

Removal of methylene blue and basic blue 41 from aqueous solutions using silica fume: A central composite design approach

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluates the effectiveness of silica fume (SF) as a sustainable and economical adsorbent for eliminating the cationic dyes Basic Blue-41 (BB-41) and Methylene Blue (MB) from aqueous solutions. Unlike conventional adsorbents, SF offers a low-cost valorization pathway for an industrial by-product, while demonstrating superior dye uptake performance. SF's morphology and surface characteristics were examined using FESEM and FTIR analyses. Batch adsorption experiments were carried out under different operational parameters, including pH, adsorbent dosage, contact time, and initial dye concentration. Equilibrium studies revealed that adsorption followed the Freundlich isotherm, indicating a heterogeneous surface with multilayer adsorption, while Langmuir analysis confirmed high maximum monolayer capacities of 108.95 mg/g for BB-41 and 189.31 mg/g for MB. Kinetic modeling showed that both dyes followed the pseudo-second-order model ($R^2 = 0.9977$ for BB-41 and $R^2 = 0.9991$ for MB), suggesting chemisorption as the dominant mechanism, involving stronger dye-surface interactions beyond physical adsorption. The optimal removal efficiency for BB-41 reached 97.12 % at pH 10, using 0.25 g of SF for 20 min with a 20 mg/L dye concentration. For MB, the maximum predicted efficiency was 98.94 % under similar conditions at pH 9.81, a dosage of 0.14 g, and 31 min contact time. These results highlight the novelty of employing SF as a high-capacity, heterogeneous, and chemisorption-driven adsorbent, underscoring its promise for practical dye-laden wastewater treatment.

1. Introduction

The global textile industry is a major source of aquatic pollution, discharging considerable volumes of wastewater laden with persistent contaminants such as synthetic dyes and heavy metals [1,2]. During dyeing operations, large quantities of water and additive chemicals are utilized to achieve desired coloration and fixation, contributing to the complex composition of dye effluents. [3,4]. Among the commonly used colorants, Methylene Blue (MB) and Basic Blue 41 (BB-41) are notable for their widespread industrial applications and environmental persistence. MB, an aromatic heterocyclic dye, is extensively used in textiles and pharmaceuticals but is classified as potentially harmful due to its toxicity, resistance to degradation, and potential to cause respiratory, digestive, and neurological symptoms upon chronic exposure [5,6]. However, it is considered toxic, carcinogenic, and non-biodegradable,

with prolonged exposure leading to respiratory issues, gastrointestinal discomfort, and neurological disorders [7,8]. Similarly, BB-41, a monoazo dye with strong stability in aqueous systems, poses ecotoxicological risks and has been associated with adverse biological effects in both humans and aquatic species [9].

Considering the significant environmental and health risks associated with these dyes, developing effective methods for their removal from wastewater has become a pressing concern [10,11]. Adsorption has emerged as a highly efficient and eco-friendly approach to dye removal, with the choice of adsorbent playing a critical role in determining performance [12–14]. Industrial and agricultural waste materials are increasingly recognized as sustainable and cost-effective adsorbents for dye removal from wastewater. Recent reviews have summarized the valorization of waste biomass, industrial by-products, and even plastic residues into efficient sorbents, highlighting adsorption mechanisms,

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performance ranges, and regeneration potential [15–17]. Key experimental studies further demonstrate the effectiveness of raw and modified wastes, such as sugarcane bagasse and *Ziziphus jujuba* seeds, supported by advanced modeling tools [18,19], while activated carbons derived from walnut shells showcase the potential of high-surface-area agro-waste sorbents [20]. The success of adsorption, however, largely depends on the properties of the adsorbent. Silica fume (SF), a fine particulate by-product of the silicon and ferrosilicon alloy industry, exhibits advantageous features such as high surface area, porosity, and chemical inertness, making it a promising candidate for pollutant removal [21,22]. Despite these properties, its potential for simultaneous removal of structurally different dyes like MB and BB-41 remains underexplored.

The central composite design (CCD) method is a popular experimental design tool, especially useful for optimizing processes involving multiple variables. It consists of a full or fractional factorial design in which each factor has two levels, along with some center points and two axial (or star) points for each factor. CCD is an efficient design method as it minimizes the number of required experimental runs while maintaining a high level of accuracy in approximating the response surface. This reduction in experiments also decreases the use of chemicals, making it a cost-effective choice for testing [3,23].

While several studies have highlighted the potential of SF as an adsorbent, most of them have focused on the removal of either heavy metals or single dye types. For instance, Wang and Chu (2011) demonstrated that SF performs better than coal ash in removing Rhodamine B from aqueous solutions [24]. Similarly, Kalkan et al. reported its high adsorption capacity for nickel [25]. However, these studies mainly focus on inorganic pollutants or single organic dyes, without considering the complexity of real textile wastewater, which often contains multiple synthetic dyes with different chemical structures and behaviors. Furthermore, most prior works do not apply statistical optimization techniques such as central composite design (CCD) to fine-tune the adsorption process.

SF is selected over other commonly used adsorbents such as activated carbon and industrial wastes due to its unique combination of cost-effectiveness, availability, and physicochemical properties. As an abundantly available by-product of the silicon and ferrosilicon industry, SF provides a sustainable and low-cost alternative to activated carbon, which, despite its high adsorption capacity, is costly to produce and regenerate. Compared to other industrial wastes, SF offers greater consistency in composition, being predominantly amorphous silica with reactive silanol groups that readily bind pollutants, while avoiding the risk of toxic element leaching often associated with wastes such as red mud or fly ash. Furthermore, its ultrafine particle size and high specific surface area enhance its adsorption potential, and its environmentally benign nature aligns with waste valorization and circular economy principles. These advantages make SF a more practical, sustainable, and reliable adsorbent for environmental applications. In this study, SF is explored for the simultaneous adsorption of two widely used but chemically distinct dyes — MB and BB-41—under varying operational conditions. The use of CCD allows for the optimization of parameters such as pH, contact time, and adsorbent dosage, ensuring efficient dye removal with minimal chemical usage. This approach addresses gaps in previous research by combining multi-dye removal, the reuse of low-cost industrial by-products, and statistical process optimization, offering a more practical and environmentally sustainable solution for textile wastewater treatment.

In the present work, silica fume (SF) is evaluated as a low-cost, sustainable adsorbent for the removal of MB and BB-41 dyes from aqueous solutions through batch experiments. The study includes a detailed analysis of SF's physicochemical characteristics using techniques such as field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM), Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), and X-ray fluorescence (XRF). Through this integrated approach, the research provides new insights into the dual dye adsorption performance of SF and offers

practical guidelines for optimizing treatment conditions in textile wastewater applications.

1.1. Materials

This study utilized two synthetic cationic dyes—Methylene Blue (MB) and Basic Blue 41 (BB-41)—commonly found in industrial effluents. Their molecular structures and spectral characteristics were used to monitor the adsorption process, with BB-41 and MB showing peak absorbance at 610 nm and 665 nm, respectively (Fig. 1).

Silica fume (SF), an amorphous silica-rich by-product, was sourced from Lorestan Ferroalloy Company (Iran). The material was sieved through a 60-mesh screen to ensure uniform particle size before use. The specific surface area of the sieved SF was measured at approximately 18 m²/g, and its composition was evaluated using X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy, revealing a high purity level (96.12 % SiO₂), along with trace components such as K₂O and Al₂O₃. Other physical characteristics obtained including bulk density (213 kg/m³) and mean pore diameter (13 μm). This high silica content indicates a chemically pure form of SF, which is favorable for adsorption processes due to its consistent surface chemistry. In this research, pH was adjusted during the process using a pH meter (AZ8686). The pH adjustments were carried out using 0.1 M solutions of hydrochloric acid (HCl) and sodium hydroxide (NaOH), added dropwise until the desired pH level was reached. No additional buffering agents were used during the experiments. The materials were then mixed using a magnetic hot plate (model TA-105, VELP, France). The morphological structure of the SF particles was examined via field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM, JSM 6400, JEOL, Japan).

The FESEM micrograph (Fig. 2) reveals that the sample is composed of densely aggregated, roughly spherical particles with a broad size distribution. The surfaces of these particles are notably rough and irregular, and numerous inter-particle voids and pores can be observed throughout the structure. Such a morphology is favorable for adsorption applications, as the high surface roughness and porous architecture provide abundant active sites and pathways for adsorbate access. This structure facilitates the adsorption of dye molecules by providing more active sites for interaction.

The FTIR spectrum of SF displayed distinct peaks that provided insights into the functional groups and molecular structure present in the material (Fig. 3). A prominent peak observed at 1114 cm⁻¹ is attributed to the symmetric stretching vibration of Si–O–Si bonds, indicating the presence of siloxane (Si–O–Si) groups. This is typical for the silica network structure found in SF. Additionally, a peak at 806 cm⁻¹ is associated with the symmetric bending vibration of Si–O–Si bonds, further confirming the siloxane groups. Another peak at 476 cm⁻¹ represents the symmetric bending vibration of Si–O–Si bonds, reinforcing the silica network's structure.

In addition to the siloxane groups, SF also contains silanol (Si–OH) groups, which are crucial for its adsorption properties. These groups are often found on the surface of silica-based materials and play an important role in interactions with dye molecules. Although the specific peak for silanol groups is typically seen around 3400 cm⁻¹, which was not distinctly labelled in the spectrum, their presence can be inferred. These Si–OH groups contribute to the hydrophilic nature of the SF surface, enhancing its ability to adsorb cationic dyes such as BB-41 and MB through hydrogen bonding and electrostatic interactions. This makes SF an effective adsorbent for the removal of these dyes from aqueous solutions.

Despite this, the role of silanol groups in adsorption can be rationalized based on surface chemistry. Si–OH groups contribute to the hydrophilic nature of the SF surface and can form hydrogen bonds with dye molecules, while deprotonated silanol groups (Si–O⁻) under neutral or slightly basic conditions provide negatively charged sites that favor electrostatic attraction with cationic dyes such as BB-41 and MB. Previous studies on silica-based adsorbents have similarly highlighted

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of (a) Basic Blue 41 and (b) Methylene Blue. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. Structure of SF based on FESEM.

Fig. 3. FTIR spectrum of SF.

electrostatic interactions as the dominant adsorption mechanism, supplemented by hydrogen bonding and van der Waals forces [26,27]. In line with this, the removal efficiency observed in this work indicates that surface charge and functional group availability play a critical role in driving adsorption.

In summary, the FTIR spectrum reveals the presence of both siloxane (Si–O–Si) and silanol (Si–OH) functional groups in SF, which are integral to its adsorption mechanism. The adsorption mechanism can be attributed to a combination of electrostatic attraction between cationic dye

molecules and negatively charged surface sites, hydrogen bonding involving Si–OH groups, and secondary interactions such as van der Waals forces. These mechanisms are consistent with reports in the literature and explain the effective dye removal performance of SF.

2. Methods

2.1. Adsorption method

To investigate the dye removal performance of silica fume (SF), adsorption experiments were conducted in a batch system. A concentrated stock solution (1000 mg/L) of each dye (MB and BB-41) was initially prepared and subsequently diluted with deionized water to achieve the desired working concentrations. In each trial, 100 mL of the dye solution was placed in Erlenmeyer flasks, and SF dosages ranging from 0.1 to 0.5 g were introduced. The mixtures were agitated at a constant speed of 300 rpm on a magnetic hot plate at 25 °C for a duration sufficient to reach equilibrium.

Following the adsorption process, the solutions were centrifuged to separate the SF, and the supernatant was analyzed using a UV–Vis spectrophotometer (UV2100, Unique, USA). The absorbance readings were taken at 665 nm and 610 nm for MB and BB-41, respectively, to quantify dye concentrations. The removal efficiency (%) was determined using the following expression [28]:

$$R = \frac{C_0 - C_L}{C_0} \quad (1)$$

C_0 is the initial dye concentration (mg/L), and C_e is the dye concentration at equilibrium (mg/L).

The adsorption capacity q (mg/g) of SF was calculated using [29]:

$$q = \frac{C_0 - C_f}{M} \times V \quad (2)$$

V is the solution volume (L) and M is the mass of SF used (g) [30].

Response surface methodology (RSM) is a set of mathematical techniques used to analyze and model processes with multiple factors and to optimize the response [31,32]. This experimental design enables process evaluation, improves process efficiency, and identifies key factors affecting the response [33–35]. In this study, the central composite design (CCD) was employed to optimize the adsorption process and to assess interactions among factors [36]. Regression analysis was used to model the response and to quantify the relationship between factors [37,38].

The one-factor-at-a-time approach is time-consuming and cannot determine interactions between factors in multi-factorial systems [39]. Therefore, in this study, CCD was applied to model and optimize the adsorption of MB and BB-41 from aqueous solutions by SF, as well as to investigate factorial interactions and their effects on the response.

2.2. Adsorption study

The efficiency of SF as an adsorbent for removing BB-41 and MB was assessed through a systematic batch adsorption study. Residual dye concentrations were quantified using UV-Vis spectrophotometry after centrifugation, allowing for accurate determination of adsorption capacities under varying experimental conditions.

The influence of pH on dye adsorption was evaluated over a range of 2 to 10. As shown in Fig. 4a, adsorption capacities increased significantly with rising pH, reaching 15.73 mg/g for MB and 16.64 mg/g for BB-41 at pH 10. This trend is attributed to enhanced electrostatic interactions: at higher pH values, the SF surface becomes increasingly negatively charged, promoting attraction of the dye molecules. Conversely, at lower pH, the surface is protonated, and the positively charged adsorbent surface repels the dyes, reducing adsorption efficiency. In acidic conditions, the higher concentration of H^+ ions also compete with dye cations for available binding sites, further limiting adsorption. As the pH increases, more negatively charged ligands are exposed on the adsorbent surface, enhancing attraction of dye ions. Quantitatively, the adsorption capacity increased by approximately 40–50 % when the pH was raised from 2 to 3 to 10, highlighting the critical role of electrostatic interactions in the adsorption process. These results are consistent with previous studies on silica-based adsorbents, which report maximum dye adsorption at alkaline pH values [40]. To determine the optimal contact time, experiments were carried out at pH 10, and adsorption was monitored over intervals ranging from 20 to 90 min (Fig. 4b.). The adsorption curve shows the characteristic two-phase process typical of dye uptake by porous adsorbents. In the first stage, a rapid increase in adsorption capacity was observed due to the high availability of active sites on the silica fume surface. This was followed by a slower stage as the active sites became progressively occupied and diffusion into internal pores controlled the process. Equilibrium was achieved within 20 min for BB-41 and 30 min for MB, indicating strong electrostatic interaction between the negatively charged SF surface and the cationic dyes under alkaline conditions [41].

The impact of adsorbent dosage on dye removal was also explored by varying the amount of SF from 0.2 to 0.5 g (Fig. 5a). An inverse relationship was observed between dosage and adsorption capacity per unit mass. Specifically, the adsorption capacity for MB decreased from 46.47 mg/g at the lowest dosage to 9.81 mg/g at the highest. A similar pattern was recorded for BB-41 (49.03 to 9.35 mg/g). Although dye removal efficiency increases with higher adsorbent dosage, the adsorption capacity per unit mass decreases because the fixed amount of dye solute becomes insufficient to saturate the much larger number of active sites

provided at higher dosages. In addition, particle aggregation at elevated dosages can reduce the effective surface area and lead to interference between adjacent binding sites, thereby lowering the efficiency of individual adsorption sites.

Initial dye concentration was another critical factor influencing adsorption behavior. As shown in Fig. 5b, increasing the dye concentration from 20 to 100 mg/L resulted in a marked increase in adsorption capacity for both dyes. This outcome is consistent with the higher driving force for mass transfer at elevated concentrations, which enhances the interaction probability between dye molecules and the SF surface.

2.3. Kinetics and isotherm study

Understanding how dyes interact with an adsorbent surface is essential for evaluating both the efficiency and the mechanism of the adsorption process. In this study, equilibrium isotherms and kinetic models were applied to describe the removal behavior of BB-41 and MB dyes on SF.

The equilibrium data in Table 1 revealed that the adsorption of both MB and BB-41 is better represented by the Freundlich isotherm, suggesting that the surface of SF is heterogeneous and offers a variety of adsorption sites with different affinities. This also implies that multi-layer adsorption occurs rather than a simple uniform monolayer. Nevertheless, the Langmuir analysis provided additional insight into the adsorption capacity. The maximum monolayer adsorption capacity was found to be 189.31 mg/g for MB and 108.95 mg/g for BB-41, confirming that SF has a strong affinity for both dyes, with a higher uptake capacity for MB. The separation factor (R_L) values obtained from the Langmuir model for both dyes were between 0 and 1, indicating that the adsorption process is favorable and spontaneous. These findings suggest that SF can function as an efficient adsorbent for dye-laden wastewater. (See Table 1.)

The kinetic study in Table 1 further supports this conclusion. Both dyes were found to follow the pseudo-second-order kinetic model, with correlation coefficients ($R^2 = 0.9977$ for BB-41 and $R^2 = 0.9991$ for MB). This fit indicates that the adsorption process is not controlled merely by physical interactions, such as diffusion, but is more likely characterized by chemisorption. In this mechanism, the dye molecules interact with the active sites of SF through electron sharing or exchange, which usually forms stronger and more specific bonds compared to physisorption.

These results suggest that the adsorption of BB-41 and MB onto SF is a heterogeneous, multilayer, and chemisorption-driven process. The higher capacity observed for MB indicates that the molecular structure

Fig. 4. The adsorption capacity of MB and BB-41 using SF a) Effect of pH (2 to 11 and 25 °C) and b) Effect of contact time (20 to 90 min at pH = 10 and 25 °C).

Fig. 5. The adsorption capacity of MB and BB-41 using SF **a)** Effect of SF dosage (0.2 to 0.5 g) and **b)** Effect of initial dye concentrations (20 to 100 mg/L). Experiments conducted at pH = 10 and 25 °C.

Table 1

Kinetic and Isotherm Parameters for the Adsorption of MB and BB-41 onto SF.

	MB	BB-41
Kinetics		
Pseudo-first order Kinetic model		
K_1	0.0491	0.0377
q_e (mg/g)	0.0345	0.0452
R^2	0.3385	0.6099
Pseudo-second order Kinetic model		
K_2 (g/mg min)	0.0417	0.0588
q_e (mg/g)	22.5750	23.8884
R^2	0.9991	0.9977
Isotherm		
Langmuir		
q_{max} (mg/g)	189.3101	108.9482
K_L (l/mg)	0.0970	0.3075
R_L	0.1467	0.0752
R^2	0.8473	0.9588
Freundlich		
K_F	16.3956	24.4589
N	1.1304	1.3059
R^2	0.9909	0.9906
Dubinin–Radushkevich		
q_s (mg/g)	44.3289	43.2213
β (mol ² /kJ)	3.7931×10^6	7.9814×10^6
E (Kj/mol)	0.004	0.025
R^2	0.9443	0.9227
Temkin		
b_T	117.3272	134.6605
A_T (l/g)	2.4972	4.6603
R^2	0.9773	0.9672

and charge distribution of the dye influence its affinity for SF, which may be attributed to stronger interactions with the available functional groups on the adsorbent surface.

2.4. CCD design

The CCD approach within RSM was employed to optimize the adsorption process by evaluating the effects of key variables: pH (A), adsorbent amount (B), contact time (C), and initial dye concentration (D). This data-driven design offers flexibility by allowing the selection of

design points from the available experimental data, enabling a comprehensive analysis without restrictions on the number of design factors. It provides a robust framework for analyzing parameter interactions and optimizing process conditions.

In this study, the adsorption process was modeled using CCD at three levels within the optimal parameter range. For instance, the optimal contact time was identified as 30 min for Methylene Blue (MB) and 20 min for Basic Blue-41 (BB-41). Therefore, the CCD levels for contact time were set at 20, 30, and 40 min, enabling a direct comparison between the two dyes.

The selected variable ranges for the CCD design were pH (8–10), adsorbent amount (0.1–0.3 g), contact time (20–40 min), and initial dye concentration (20–60 mg/L). Modeling was carried out using Design-Expert software (version 21) to evaluate the interactions and determine the optimal conditions. This approach allowed for efficient correlation of experimental conditions with adsorption performance, leading to successful optimization of the process. The experimental response values obtained from the CCD design are presented in Table 2.

Furthermore, ANOVA result for BB-41 and MB are presented in Table 3 and Table 4, respectively. In general, the factors with P -values below 0.05 are considered statistically significant. Moreover, the model is considered acceptable if the F -value is greater than one.

According to the Table 3, the impact of pH, adsorbent dosage, initial concentration, the interaction between pH and amount of adsorbent, the quadratic effect of pH, and the quadratic effect of concentration are important parameters influencing the BB-41 model.

According to Table 4, the impact of pH, adsorbent dosage, initial concentration, and the interactions between pH and adsorbent dosage, pH and concentration, adsorbent dosage and time, adsorbent dosage and concentration, time and concentration, well as the quadratic effect of adsorbent dosage, are significant parameters impacting on the design model for the MB experiment.

The final quadratic model for BB-41, with an R^2 of 0.9684, is given as:

$$R1 = -234/55 + 74/63 A - 571/16B + 0/091C + 0/81D + 67/83AB - 0/061 AC - 0/01 CE - 0/33 BCE + 0/84BD + 2/98 \times 10^{-3}CD - 4/29A^2 - 222/08B^2 + 6/31C^2 - 9/06 \times 10^{-3} D^2.$$

Similarly, the final quadratic model for MB, with an R^2 of 0.9509, is:

$$R2 = 101/26 + 5/14 A - 173/44B + 0/58C - 1/69D + 23/67AB + 0/04 AC + 0/19 CE + 3/22 BCE + 2/87BD - 0/013CD - 0/82A^2 - 824/86B^2 - 0/02C^2 - 2/27 \times 10^{-3} D^2 (4-4).$$

Where R1 and R2 represent the removal percentage, A = pH, B = adsorbent dosage, C = contact time, and D = initial concentration.

Based on these results, the highest removal percentage for BB-41 was achieved 97.12 % at pH = 10, adsorbent dosage = 0.25 g, contact time = 20 min, and an initial concentration = 20 mg/L. This prediction by the

Table 2
Experimental response values of the CCD design for MB and BB-41.

Run	A	B	C	D	BB-41	MB
					R1 _{predicted}	R2 _{predicted}
1	10	0.3	40	20	92.52	79.62
2	8	0.1	20	60	90.68	88.14
3	9	0.2	30	40	95.81	95.92
4	9	0.2	30	20	90.47	94.12
5	8	0.1	40	60	93.22	78.74
6	8	0.3	20	60	66.88	72.70
7	10	0.1	40	60	95.01	90.38
8	9	0.2	30	40	95.81	95.92
9	8	0.3	40	20	62.65	74.46
10	10	0.1	40	20	91.21	95.67
11	9	0.2	30	40	95.81	95.92
12	9	0.3	30	40	87.96	77.46
13	9	0.2	30	40	95.81	95.92
14	10	0.2	30	40	98.34	97.32
15	9	0.2	30	40	95.80	95.92
16	10	0.3	40	60	96.99	97.31
17	10	0.1	20	20	93.50	94.29
18	8	0.3	40	60	68.07	76.19
19	9	0.1	30	40	96.21	93.20
20	10	0.1	20	60	94.92	96.44
21	8	0.2	30	40	82.98	91.72
22	9	0.2	20	40	96.71	94.70
23	9	0.2	40	40	96.16	97.13
24	8	0.3	20	20	63.84	60.19
25	9	0.2	30	60	93.89	97.73
26	10	0.3	20	60	98.24	93.81
27	10	0.3	20	20	96.15	65.35
28	8	0.1	20	20	88.32	98.61
29	9	0.2	30	40	95.81	95.92
30	8	0.1	40	20	88.47	97.63

software closely match the experimental results. For MB, the maximum removal percentage was obtained 98.94 % at pH = 9.81, adsorbent dosage = 0.14 g, contact time = 31 min, and initial concentration = 20 mg/L, which also showed close agreement with the experimental results.

2.5. Comparison study

The optimum conditions for the adsorption of BB-41 and MB using untreated and unmodified SF were pH of 10 and 9.81, adsorbent dosages of 0.25 g and 0.14 g, contact times of 20 and 31 min, and initial dye concentration of 20 mg/L, respectively. Under these optimized conditions, the adsorption efficiencies reached 97.12 % for BB-41 and 98.94 % for MB. These results were compared with previous studies employing

Table 3
ANOVA results for adsorption of BB-41.

Source	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Mean square	F-value	p-value Prob > F
Model	3227.11	14	230.51	32.80	<0.0001
A-pH	1308.53	1	1308.53	186.21	<0.0001
B-m	569.17	1	569.17	81.00	<0.0001
C-time	1.36	1	1.36	0.19	0.6666
D-concentration	52.68	1	52.68	7.50	0.0153
AB	736.04	1	736.04	104.74	<0.0001
AC	5.96	1	5.96	0.85	0.3720
AD	0.89	1	0.89	0.13	0.7263
BC	1.79	1	1.79	0.25	0.6209
BD	0.46	1	0.46	0.065	0.8026
CD	5.69	1	5.69	0.81	0.3824
A ²	47.87	1	47.87	6.81	0.0197
B ²	12.78	1	12.78	1.82	0.1975
C ²	1.03	1	1.03	0.15	0.7072
D ²	34.05	1	34.05	4.85	0.0438
Residual	105.41	15	7.03		
Lack of fit	74.04	10	7.40	1.18	0.4534
Pure Error	31.37	5	6.27		
Cor Total	3332.51	29			

similar methodologies, as shown in Table 5. The outcomes demonstrate that raw, unmodified SF exhibits high adsorption efficiency, comparable to or exceeding that of chemically treated or engineered adsorbents, thereby eliminating the need for complex surface modifications.

2.6. Future works

SF presents several advantages as a low-cost and effective adsorbent for cationic dyes due to its abundant silanol and siloxane functional groups. However, several challenges must be addressed for real-world applications. Aggregation of SF particles can reduce available surface area, while the presence of competing ions or other contaminants in complex wastewater may lower adsorption efficiency. Additionally, regeneration, reuse, and safe disposal of spent adsorbent require careful consideration to maintain performance. Future studies should focus on examining the regeneration and reusability of SF to ensure long-term stability and performance across multiple adsorption cycles. A deeper understanding of adsorption mechanisms is also needed: although the Freundlich isotherm best described the equilibrium data, advanced surface characterization and modeling could clarify the specific interactions responsible for multilayer chemisorption. Moreover, exploring the application of SF to a wider range of contaminants,

Table 4
ANOVA results for adsorption of MB.

Source	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	MS	F-value	p-value Prob > F
Model	3505.83	14	250.42	20.73	<0.0001
A-pH	317.45	1	317.45	26.30	0.0001
B-m	1115.56	1	1115.56	92.42	<0.0001
C-time	26.60	1	26.60	2.20	0.1584
D-concentration	58.68	1	58.68	4.86	0.0435
AB	89.68	1	89.68	7.43	0.0156
AC	2.40	1	2.40	0.20	0.6618
AD	254.52	1	254.52	21.09	0.0004
BC	166.34	1	166.34	13.78	0.0021
BD	527.69	1	527.69	43.72	<0.0001
CD	116.13	1	116.13	9.62	0.0073
A ²	1.75	1	1.75	0.15	0.7084
B ²	176.28	1	176.28	14.61	0.0017
C ²	5.96	1	5.96	0.49	0.4928
D ²	2.13	1	2.13	0.18	0.6805
Residual	181.05	15	12.07		
Lack of fit	164.75	10	16.48	5.05	0.0438
Pure Error	16.30	5	3.26		
Cor Total	3686.88	29			

Table 5
Comparison of the adsorption performance of SF with other adsorbents in literature.

Adsorbent	Optimal pH	Kinetics	Isotherm q_{\max} : mg/g	Equilibrium Time (min)	Optimal Conditions (RSM)	Reference
silica fume (SF)	10	Pseudo-second-order	Freundlich q_{\max} : 189- MB 109.9- BB-41	20 min (BB-41) 30 min (MB)	pH: 10, Adsorbent Amount: 0.25 g, Time: 20 min, Concentration: 20 mg/L (BB-41); pH: 9.81, Adsorbent Amount: 0.14 g, Time: 31 min, Concentration: 20 mg/L (MB)	Present study
silica-alumina oxide	5	pseudo-second order	Freundlich q_{\max} :47.1	240 min	- Adsorbate: Reactive Black 5	[42]
periodic mesoporous organic silica (PMO) nanoparticles	3	pseudo-second-order	Langmuir q_{\max} :17.07 Ca^{2+}	300 min	-	[43]
Schiff base-modified silica gel particles	5	pseudo-second-order	Langmuir q_{\max} : 5.46 - Cu^{2+}	90 min	-	[44]
silica gel synthesized from chemical glass bottle waste	8	pseudo-second-order	Langmuir q_{\max} : 82.02 - MB	45 min	99.41 % pH 8, time of 45 min, adsorbent mass of 60 mg, initial concentration dye: 40 mg/L	[45]
magnetite nanoparticles modified with pectin shell and silica/pectin double shell	8	Pseudo-second-order	Sips q_{\max} : 27.22	120 min	-	[46]
<i>Juglans Regia</i> (walnut shell)	7	Pseudo-second-order	Langmuir q_{\max} : 49.28	60 min	adsorption efficiency: 94.6 % (ANN) and 93.2 % (RSM)	[47]
Silica fume–metakaolin based geopolymer	7	-	-	60 min	Cu^{2+} removal efficiency (99.62 %) Adsorbate: copper	[48,49]
Amine-Functionalized Mesoporous Silica Prepared from Silica Fume	2	Pseudo-second-order	Langmuir q_{\max} : 82.05	600 min	-	[50]
Amino-functionalized mesoporous silica composite (Silica fume modified with DETA-TMC)	5	Pseudo-second-order	Langmuir q_{\max} :255.7	30 min	- Adsorbate: bromophenol	[51]

including anionic dyes, heavy metals, and pharmaceuticals, and scaling up from batch experiments to continuous-flow systems, will be essential to evaluate real-world feasibility. Integrating life cycle assessment and cost–benefit analyses can further validate SF's role as a sustainable and valorized industrial by-product.

The reuse of SF as an adsorbent also offers significant environmental and economic benefits in line with circular economy principles. By valorizing an industrial by-product, SF reduces waste disposal and minimizes the environmental footprint associated with silica production. Its low cost compared to conventional adsorbents provides an economically attractive alternative for wastewater treatment. Implementing SF in adsorption processes promotes resource efficiency and sustainability, demonstrating how industrial residues can be converted into value-added materials while supporting environmentally responsible and cost-effective treatment strategies.

3. Conclusion

In this investigation, unmodified SF was demonstrated to be an efficient, sustainable, and low-cost adsorbent for the removal of the cationic dyes BB-41 and MB from aqueous solutions. Morphological analysis using FESEM confirmed the inherently porous and spherical structure of SF, which facilitates the adsorption process by providing abundant active sites. FTIR analysis revealed functional groups that facilitate strong dye–surface interactions. The adsorption performance, particularly for MB, was notably high, aligning well with the predictions generated by the Central Composite Design (CCD) optimization model. These findings validate both the material's natural efficacy and the robustness of the applied statistical approach. Equilibrium studies showed that adsorption followed the Freundlich isotherm, indicating heterogeneous multilayer adsorption, while the Langmuir model confirmed a high monolayer adsorption capacity for both dyes. The separation factor values further demonstrated that the process is favorable and spontaneous. In addition, kinetic analysis revealed that both dyes followed the pseudo-second-order model, suggesting that

chemisorption governs the adsorption mechanism through strong interactions between the dyes and the active sites of SF. Overall, these results not only demonstrate SF's high affinity and capacity for dye removal but also highlight its novelty as a valorized industrial by-product that functions effectively without chemical modification. Thus, unmodified SF offers a practical and environmentally sustainable solution for dye-laden wastewater remediation.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Shohre Mortazavi: Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Mika Sillanpää:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Ebrahim Najafi Kani:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources.

Consent to participate

All authors agreed to participate in the publication of the research article in Results in Chemistry.

Consent for publication

It is to the consent of all the authors to publish this study in Results in Chemistry.

Ethical approval

The research does not involve any ethical issue regarding the use of living organisms or humans in research activities.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

References

- J.A. Oyetade, R.L. Machunda, A. Hilonga, Fenton-mediated solar-driven photocatalysis of industrial dye effluent with polyaniline impregnated with activated TiO₂-Nps, *J. Photochem. Photobiol.* 20 (2024) 100231, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpap.2024.100231>.
- S.K. Das, Agro-waste based biomass residues valorization for effective adsorption of heavy metal, *Environ. Monit. Assess.* 196 (11) (2024) 1058, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-024-13258-x>.
- P.O. Isibor, Application of Nanochitosan in fish detoxification/Nano-based depuration, in: P.O. Isibor, A.O. Adeogun, A.A. Enuneku (Eds.), *Nanochitosan-Based Enhancement of Fisheries and Aquaculture: Aligning with Sustainable Development Goal 14 – Life Below Water*, Springer Nature, Switzerland, Cham, 2024, pp. 265–280, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-52261-1_11.
- V.V. Devi, R. Lakshminpathy, S.V. Prabhu, A. Daoud, A. Saud, M. Sillanpaa, Batch and continuous adsorptive removal of brilliant green dye using modified jamun seed powder: RSM based optimization, *Chem. Eng. Commun.* 212 (1) (2025) 50–63, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00986445.2024.2409169>.
- S.M. El-Kousy, H.G. El-Shorbagy, M.A.A. El-Ghaffar, Chitosan/montmorillonite composites for fast removal of methylene blue from aqueous solutions, *Mater. Chem. Phys.* 254 (2020) 123236, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2020.123236>.
- A. Pandey, B. Ashish, B. Bhaduri, Synthesis of magnetite nanoparticles deposited on heat-treated graphitic carbon nitride for the removal of methylene blue dye molecules by adsorption, *Chem. Eng. Commun.* 212 (6) (2025) 922–949, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00986445.2024.2445225>.
- D. Ramutshatsha-Makhwedzha, A. Mavhungu, M.L. Moropeng, R. Mbaya, Activated carbon derived from waste orange and lemon peels for the adsorption of methyl orange and methylene blue dyes from wastewater, *Heliyon* 8 (8) (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e09930>.
- P.O. Oladoye, T.O. Ajiboye, E.O. Omotola, O.J. Oyewola, Methylene blue dye: Toxicity and potential technologies for elimination from (waste) water, *Res. Eng. Des.* (2022) 100678, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2022.100678>.
- P. Saravanan, B.P. Thillainayagam, G. Ravindiran, J. Josephraj, Evaluation of the adsorption capacity of Cocos Nucifera shell derived biochar for basic dyes sequestration from aqueous solution, *Energy Sources, Part A* (2020) 1–17.
- G.A.A.M. Al-Hazmi, A.A. Alayyafi, M.G. El-Desouky, A.A. El-Bindary, Chitosan-nano CuO composite for removal of mercury (II): box-Behnken design optimization and adsorption mechanism, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.* 261 (2024) 129769, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2024.129769>.
- J. Zhao, G. Wang, X. Dong, X. Zhang, Adsorption and photocatalytic regeneration property of biochar-Bi₂WO₆ composite, *J. Nanopart. Res.* 26 (6) (2024) 130, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11051-024-06016-0>.
- J. Joseph, A. Väisänen, A.B. Patil, M. Lahtinen, The effect of synthesis conditions on the in situ grown MIL-100(Fe)-chitosan beads: interplay between structural properties and arsenic adsorption, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 463 (2024) 132893, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2023.132893>.
- S. Shokri, N. Shariatifar, E. Molaee-Aghaee, G. Jahed Khaniki, P. Sadighara, M. A. Faramarzi, Modeling sunset yellow removal from fruit juice samples by a novel chitosan-nickel ferrite nano sorbent, *Sci. Rep.* 14 (1) (2024) 208, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-50284-0>.
- E. Allahkarami, E. Allahkarami, A. Azadmehr, M.E. Shahrabadi, Kinetics and statistical physics modeling of heavy metal ions adsorption onto functionalized pyrite composite: experimental and modeling, results, *Chemistry* (2025) 102536, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rechem.2025.102536>.
- M. Chahal, S. Kumari, A. Bhattacharya, M.C. Garg, Evaluating sustainable agricultural waste biomass for methylene blue adsorption in wastewater treatment: a state-of-the-art review, *Biores. Technol. Rep.* 28 (2024) 101983, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biteb.2024.101983>.
- S. Kumari, J. Chowdhry, M. Kumar, M.C. Garg, Machine learning (ML): an emerging tool to access the production and application of biochar in the treatment of contaminated water and wastewater, *Groundwater Sust. Devel.* 26 (2024) 101243, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gsd.2024.101243>.
- S. Kumari, N.K. Agrawal, A. Agarwal, A. Kumar, N. Malik, D. Goyal, V.D. Rajput, T. Minkina, P. Sharma, M.C. Garg, A prominent *Streptomyces* sp. biomass-based biosorption of zinc (II) and Lead (II) from aqueous solutions: isotherm and kinetic, *Separations* 10 (7) (2023), <https://doi.org/10.3390/separations10070393>.
- S. Kumari, J. Chowdhry, P. Sharma, S. Agarwal, M. Chandra Garg, Integrating artificial neural networks and response surface methodology for predictive modeling and mechanistic insights into the detoxification of hazardous MB and CV dyes using *Saccharum officinarum* L. biomass, *Chemosphere* 344 (2023) 140262, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2023.140262>.
- A. Guediri, A. Bouguettoucha, H. Tahraoui, D. Chebli, J. Zhang, A. Amrane, L. Khezami, A.A. Assadi, The enhanced adsorption capacity of Ziziphos jujuba stones modified with Ortho-phosphoric acid for organic dye removal: a Gaussian process regression approach, *Water* 16 (9) (2024), <https://doi.org/10.3390/w16091208>.
- A.E. Kuyucu, A. Selçuk, Y. Önal, İ. Alacabey, K. Erol, Effective removal of dyes from aqueous systems by waste-derived carbon adsorbent: physicochemical characterization and adsorption studies, *Sci. Rep.* 15 (1) (2025) 28835, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-13685-x>.
- Nisreen S. Ali, Talib M. Albayati, I.K. Salih, Studying the kinetics and removal mechanism of the methylene blue dye in a continuous adsorption process using prepared mesoporous materials, *Water Practice Technol.* 19 (7) (2024) 2799–2815, <https://doi.org/10.2166/wpt.2024.162>.
- S. Mortazavi, E. Najafi Kani, RSM optimization of direct Orange 26 adsorption on low-cost silica fume adsorbent, *Journal of the Turkish chemical society section B, Chem. Eng.* 6 (2) (2023) 35–44, <https://doi.org/10.58692/jotcsb.1240859>.
- G. Torğüt, T. Mehtap, Z. Meşe, Modeling and optimization of indigo carmine adsorption from aqueous solutions using a novel polymer adsorbent: RSM-CCD, *Chem. Eng. Commun.* 207 (8) (2020) 1157–1170, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00986445.2020.1731480>.
- Y. Wang, W. Chu, Adsorption and removal of a xanthene dye from aqueous solution using two solid wastes as adsorbents, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 50 (14) (2011) 8734–8741, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie1024497>.
- E. Kalkan, H. Nadaroglu, N. Celebi, Use of silica fume as low-cost adsorbent material for nickel removal from aqueous solutions, *Asian J. Chem.* 26 (18) (2014), <https://doi.org/10.14233/ajchem.2014.16786>.
- T. Wang, Y. Sun, S. Wang, X. Li, Y. Yue, Q. Gao, Effective adsorption of methyl Orange on Organo-silica nanoparticles functionalized by a multi-hydroxyl-containing Gemini surfactant: a joint experimental and theoretical study, *ACS Omega* 6 (28) (2021) 18014–18023, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.1c01788>.
- T. Shen, L. Wang, Q. Zhao, S. Guo, M. Gao, Single and simultaneous adsorption of basic dyes by novel organo-vermiculite: a combined experimental and theoretical study, *Colloids Surf. A Physicochem. Eng. Asp.* 601 (2020) 125059, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2020.125059>.
- J.P.N. Tejeogue, R. Djakba, C.G. Fotsop, N. Dobe, S. Mouhamadou, B. Wangmene, M. Harouna, Systematic metronidazole adsorption performance onto montmorillonite clay: parametric study, process modelling and RSM optimisation, *Results Chem.* 14 (2025) 102153, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rechem.2025.102153>.
- S. Mortazavi, M. Sillanpaa, D. Bose, Innovative Nanopolymers for adsorption of pollutants from water, *Int. J. Environ. Anal. Chem.* (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1080/03067319.2024.2426003>.
- E. Worch, Adsorption technology in water treatment: fundamentals, processes, and modeling, *Walter de Gruyter GmbH & Co KG*, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110240238>.
- S. Samarbaaf, Y.T. Birgani, M. Yazdani, A.A. Babaei, A comparative removal of two dyes from aqueous solution using modified oak waste residues: process optimization using response surface methodology, *J. Ind. Eng. Chem.* 73 (2019) 67–77. Doi: Doi: 10.1016/j.jiec.2018.12.011.
- R. Prasad, K.D. Yadav, Use of response surface methodology and artificial neural network approach for methylene blue removal by adsorption onto water hyacinth, *Water Conservation Manage.* 4 (2) (2020) 83–89. Doi: <http://doi.org/10.26480/wcm.02.2020.83.89>.
- S. Kumari, J. Chowdhry, A. Choudhury, S. Agarwal, P. Narad, M.C. Garg, Machine learning approaches for the treatment of textile wastewater using sugarcane bagasse (*Saccharum officinarum*) biochar, *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 32 (32) (2025) 19462–19480, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-024-31826-z>.
- M.S. Manzar, G. Khan, P.V. dos Santos Lins, M. Zubair, S.U. Khan, R. Selvasembian, L. Meili, N.I. Blaisi, M. Nawaz, H.A. Aziz, RSM-CCD optimization approach for the adsorptive removal of Eriochrome black T from aqueous system using steel slag-based adsorbent: characterization, isotherm, Kinetic Modeling Thermodynamic AnalJ. *Molecular Liq.* 339 (2021) 116714, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2021.116714>.
- Q.S. Mateen, S.U. Khan, D.T. Islam, N.A. Khan, I.H. Farooqi, Copper (II) removal in a column reactor using electrocoagulation: parametric optimization by response surface methodology using central composite design, *Water Environ. Res.* 92 (9) (2020) 1350–1362, <https://doi.org/10.1002/wer.1332>.
- Y. Achour, L. Bahsis, E.-H. Ablouh, H. Yazid, M.R. Laamari, M. El Haddad, Insight into adsorption mechanism of Congo red dye onto Bombax Buonopozense bark activated-carbon using central composite design and DFT studies, *Surf Interfaces* 23 (2021) 100977, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surf.2021.100977>.
- I. Hasan, D. Bhatia, S. Walia, P. Singh, Removal of malachite green by polyacrylamide-g-chitosan γ -Fe₂O₃ nanocomposite-an application of central composite design, *Groundwater Sust. Devel.* 11 (2020) 100378, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gsd.2020.100378>.
- J. Bayuo, K.B. Pelig-Ba, M.A. Abukari, Optimization of adsorption parameters for effective removal of lead (II) from aqueous solution, *Phys. Chem. Indian J* 14 (1) (2019) 1–25.
- P. Karoui, R.B. Arfi, K. Mougine, A. Ghorbal, A.A. Assadi, A. Amrane, Synthesis of novel biocomposite powder for simultaneous removal of hazardous ciprofloxacin and methylene blue: central composite design, kinetic and isotherm studies using Brouers-Sotolongo family models, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 387 (5) (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2019.121675Get>.
- E. Kalkan, H. Nadaroglu, N. Celebi, G. Tozsin, Removal of textile dye reactive black 5 from aqueous solution by adsorption on laccase-modified silica fume, *Desalin.*

- Water Treat. 52 (31) (2014) 6122–6134, <https://doi.org/10.1080/19443994.2013.811114>.
- [41] I. Loulidi, F. Boukhlifi, M. Ouchabi, A. Amar, M. Jabri, A. Kali, S. Chraïbi, C. Hadey, F. Aziz, Adsorption of crystal violet onto an agricultural waste residue: kinetics, isotherm, thermodynamics, and mechanism of adsorption, *Sci. World J.* 2020 (1) (2020) 5873521, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/5873521>.
- [42] M. Wawrzkiwicz, M. Wiśniewska, A. Wołowicz, V.M. Gun'ko, V.I. Zarko, Mixed silica-alumina oxide as sorbent for dyes and metal ions removal from aqueous solutions and wastewaters, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* 250 (2017) 128–147, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micromeso.2017.05.016>.
- [43] Y. Si, J. Li, B. Cui, D. Tang, L. Yang, V. Murugadoss, S. Maganti, M. Huang, Z. Guo, Janus phenol-formaldehyde resin and periodic mesoporous organic silica nanoadsorbent for the removal of heavy metal ions and organic dyes from polluted water, *Adv. Compos. Hybrid Mater.* 5 (2) (2022) 1180–1195, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42114-022-00446-x>.
- [44] M. Koorepazan Moftakhar, Z. Dousti, M.R. Yaftian, M. Ghorbanloo, Investigation of heavy metal ions adsorption behavior of silica-supported Schiff base ligands, *Desalin. Water Treat.* 57 (56) (2016) 27396–27408, <https://doi.org/10.1080/19443994.2016.1170638>.
- [45] P.A.N. Suprpto, Y.L. Azizah, NI'MAH, Silica gel from chemical glass bottle waste as adsorbent for methylene blue: optimization using BBD, *J. Renewable Mater.* 11 (12) (2023), <https://doi.org/10.32604/jrm.2023.031210>.
- [46] O.A. Attallah, M.A. Al-Ghobashy, M. Nebsen, M.Y. Salem, Removal of cationic and anionic dyes from aqueous solution with magnetite/pectin and magnetite/silica/pectin hybrid nanocomposites: kinetic, isotherm and mechanism analysis, *RSC Adv.* 6 (14) (2016) 11461–11480, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C5RA23452B>.
- [47] S. Kumari, S. Singh, S.-L. Lo, P. Sharma, S. Agarwal, M.C. Garg, Machine learning and modelling approach for removing methylene blue from aqueous solutions: optimization, kinetics and thermodynamics studies, *J. Taiwan Inst. Chem. Eng.* 166 (2025) 105361, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtice.2024.105361>.
- [48] P. Arokiasamy, M.M.A.B. Abdullah, E. Arifi, N.H. Jamil, M.A. Othuman Mydin, S. Z. Abd Rahim, A.V. Sandu, S. Ishak, Sustainable geopolymer adsorbents utilizing silica fume as a partial replacement for metakaolin in the removal of copper ion from synthesized copper solution, case studies, *Constr. Mater.* 22 (2025) e04142, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cscm.2024.e04142>.
- [49] Y. Zhang, H. Qi, Y. Li, Y. Zhang, J. Sun, Preparation and characterization of a porous silicate material from silica fume, *Korean J. Chem. Eng.* 34 (12) (2017) 3185–3194, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11814-017-0228-5>.
- [50] X. Li, C. Han, W. Zhu, W. Ma, Y. Luo, Y. Zhou, J. Yu, K. Wei, Cr(VI) removal from aqueous by adsorption on amine-functionalized mesoporous silica prepared from silica fume, *J. Chemother.* 2014 (1) (2014) 765856, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/765856>.
- [51] I. Khan Rind, A. Sari, M. Tuzen, T.A. Saleh, Adsorption of bromophenol blue from aquatic media using polymer-modified silica fume: factorial design optimization, kinetic evaluation and adsorption mechanism, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.* 168 (2024) 112953, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.inoche.2024.112953>.